

The oral trial process in criminal matters

The oral trial process in criminal matters can be divided into several phases. This article by [retired judge](#) Cindy Imperato describes the phases from opening statements to appeal.

Cindy Imperato shares that when the court is ready for the oral trial to take place, the two parties give the opening statements. When it comes to a criminal case, the prosecutor speaks first. To begin with, the attorney gives a summary of the facts to be presented. The attorney for the other party may make a similar presentation or may save the opening statements until later in the oral proceedings when the defense proceedings begin. Both attorneys can choose not to give opening statements.

Direct questioning

[Cindy Imperato](#) indicates that the tax attorney will begin the oral trial by summoning the witnesses and asking them questions. It's called direct questioning.

In all oral trials, witnesses take an oath or affirm that what they say in court is the truth. All oral trial evidence, including testimony and actual evidence such as documents, weapons, or clothing, must be admissible in accordance with the Arizona Evidence Rules before it is admitted and demonstrated to the jury. . The judge will decide if the evidence and testimony are admissible according to the rules.

Cindy Imperato shares that in the oral trial in criminal matters, the tax attorney presents the evidence and the testimony of the witnesses to try to prove that the accused has committed the wrongful act. The defendant's attorney may present evidence and witnesses to show that the defendant did not commit the crime or to create a reasonable doubt as to the defendant's guilt. The accused is considered innocent of having committed the wrongful act of which he is accused until his guilt has been proven.